

MUHANDISLIK

& IQTISODIYOT

№4

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

2025
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Milliy nashrlar

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08.00.00 – Iqtisodiyot fanlar

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- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
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- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
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- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
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- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
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- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti

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STRENGTHENING AND ENHANCING THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES FOR SUSTAINABLE GROWTH

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Abstract: The thesis of the article explored the essence and objectives of the export policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the export management system. An analysis of the current state of the textile industry and its export activities was conducted. Additionally, "Konteks Tashkent" LLC presented practical recommendations aimed at improving the export potential of the Republic.

Keywords: competitive advantage, competition, economic globalization, integration into the world market, strategic vision.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasining eksport siyosatining mohiyati va maqsadlari, shuningdek, eksportni boshqarish tizimi yoritilgan. Tekstil sanoatining hozirgi holati va uning eksport faoliyati tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, "Konteks Toshkent" MChJ tomonidan respublikaning eksport salohiyatini oshirishga qaratilgan amaliy tavsiyalar taqdim etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: raqobat ustunligi, raqobat, iqtisodiy globallashuv, jahon bozoriga integratsiya, strategik qarash.

Аннотация: В статье рассмотрены сущность и цели экспортной политики Республики Узбекистан, а также система управления экспортом. Проведен анализ текущего состояния текстильной промышленности и ее экспортной деятельности. Кроме того, ООО «Konteks Tashkent» представило практические рекомендации, направленные на повышение экспортного потенциала республики.

Ключевые слова: конкурентное преимущество, конкуренция, экономическая глобализация, интеграция в мировой рынок, стратегическое видение.

INTRODUCTION

The textile industry in Uzbekistan boasts a rich heritage of cotton fiber processing, rooted in the traditions of the Great Silk Road. Uzbek artisans have gained international acclaim for their exquisite silk and satin fabrics.

With the increasing demand for natural fiber products in today's market, Uzbekistan is well-positioned to become an exporter not only of raw cotton but also of finished textiles and light industrial goods. The President's decision from 2019-12-18 outlined a new framework for developing and financing state programs, highlighting key tasks aimed at enhancing exports.

This sector plays a crucial role in the production of consumer goods, significantly contributing to industrial output and ensuring the saturation of domestic markets. Additionally, it generates numerous jobs, particularly for women, thereby fostering demographic stability in industrial regions. The growth

of export potential is vital, as it directly influences the republic's overall economic development and contributes to improving living standards for its citizens.

Therefore, Uzbekistan's influence and capabilities on the global stage are shaped by its economic and social advancements. Enhancing the export potential of the textile industry remains a top priority for the country, emphasizing the strategic importance of this issue.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The theoretical and methodological aspects of managing production inventories in cotton-textile clusters have been examined in the works of both domestic and foreign scholars, including N.M. Muminova, O.D. Djuraev, N. Yuldashev, B. Tursunov, B.A. Paluanov, A.P. Pirmatov, A.R. Tolybaev, M.A. Abatov, N.A. Khromykh, V.A. Agafonov, V.I. Malyuk, R.M. Difrancesco, and A. Huchzermeier.

The concept of a circular economy in relation to optimizing production inventories in the textile industry has been analyzed in the research of B.S. Mashukova, V.A. Titov, O.L. Morozov, R.A. Karadjaev, and Liu Syczy.

Operational aspects of inventory management in cotton-textile clusters have been studied by A.A. Sultanov, G.D. Khalmatjanova, Z.M. Mirzaakhmadov, Y.S. Shakirova, M.A. Matveeva, R.A. Isaev, A.D. Kilimova, R. Kaplan, D. Norton, A. Brown, and W. Malsam.

Processes of digitalization in managing production inventories have been explored in the works of E.A. Islandkina, N.V. Kurganova, M.A. Filin, D.S. Chernyaev, A.G. Shaklein, D.E. Namiot, V.N. Tregubov, D. JiuJun, M.A. Waller, and S.E. Fawcett.

Foreign experience in managing production inventories in cotton-textile clusters has been synthesized by the author based on the analysis of works by S. Ma, Y. Lin, R.M. Difrancesco, A. Huchzermeier, A.J. Schmitt, M. Singh, M.D. Rossetti, R.R. Hill, and B. Johansson.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In preparing the article, such research methods as the method of horizontal and vertical analysis, the formal-logical method, the method of scientific abstraction, and econometric analysis were used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The light industry of Uzbekistan has a long-standing tradition of processing cotton fibers. Historically, the Great Silk Road passed through Uzbekistan, where goods crafted by local artisans – particularly silk and satin fabrics – gained international acclaim.

Considering the rising global demand for products made from natural fibers, it is important to highlight that Uzbekistan has significant potential to be recognized as an exporter not only of raw cotton but also of finished textiles and light industrial goods.

The textile sector, which focuses on consumer goods, plays a central role in industrial production, significantly saturating local markets. Additionally, this industry creates numerous jobs, particularly for women, helping to maintain demographic balance in industrial regions. A key factor in this context is the growth of export potential, which is directly linked to the overall economic development of the republic and the living standards of its population.

As of 2023-01-01, there are 1,512 industrial enterprises within the "Uztoqimaliksanoat" association, including 369 textile enterprises and 1,143 operating in the knitting industry. Currently, one-third of all industrial employees work in the light industry, which accounts for 13.4% of total industrial output and 55% of consumer goods.

The light industry in our republic is experiencing rapid development. In 1991, only 7% of the cotton fiber produced was processed; today, that figure has risen to 45%. According to Presidential Resolution No. 2687 from 2018-12-21, the goal for 2023 is to increase cotton fiber processing to 76%. The priority is to fully process 100% of the cotton raw materials produced and to boost export volumes by 2.5 times, while tripling overall production (table 1).

Table 1. Dynamics of product production volume in 2016-2019 in the enterprises of the «Uztoqmachilik sanoat» association.

Product types	Unit of measure	2020 y.	2021 y.	2022 y.	2023 y.
Cotton thread	thousand tons	257,8	307,2	348,6	385,2
Ready yarn gauze	million m2	154,9	182,9	198,7	238,4
Silk thread	tons	1016,4	1077,7	1230,1	1291,5
Knitted fabric	tons	47700	53400	62800	69900
Knitted goods	million piece	166,3	184,7	219,4	274,3
Hosiery products	a thousand pairs	29200	38900	46100	49300
Sewing products at wholesale prices	million soum	28700	30800	37900	49300
Export	million dollar	865,1	1050,1	1170,0	1350,0

Currently, the annual processing capacity of cotton fiber enterprises exceeds 522,000 tons. The production capabilities for yarn, including mixed and silk yarns, reach 276 million square meters, with 101,000 tons of knitted fabric produced annually. The capacity for sewing and knitted products stands at 270.5 million units, while garments and hosiery products can produce 45 million pairs annually.

From 2020 to 2023, there has been a noticeable trend of increasing raw cotton processing volumes within the “Uztoqimaliksanoat” association. In 2020, 285,000 tons of raw cotton were processed, followed by 260,000 tons in 2021. In 2022, this figure rose to 420,000 tons, and by 2023, processing reached 642,000 tons, marking a growth rate of 152.98% compared to 2022.

Examining the production of cotton yarn in the “Uztoqimaliksanoat” association reveals that production volumes were 257,800 tons in 2020, 307,200 tons in 2021, and 348,600 tons in 2022. However, it is important to note that the production capacity of spinning enterprises is not fully utilized. During this period, the utilization rates were 66.1%, 73.1%, and 75.8%, respectively. In 2023, cotton yarn production increased to 385,200 tons, with utilization rates climbing to 81%. This represents a 110.5% increase in production compared to 2022, with a utilization rate of 107%.

In terms of yarn produced in weaving enterprises within the “Uztoqimaliksanoat” association, the figures were 165 million linear meters in 2020, 182.9 million in 2021, and 189.1 million in 2022. The growth rate from 2021 to 2020 was 110.8%, while the increase from 2022 to 2021 was 103.4%. In 2023, production reached 238.4 million linear meters, a 125.9% increase compared to 2022. Nonetheless, the production capacities of weaving enterprises within the association remain underutilized, indicating potential for increased output through better utilization of existing facilities (table 2).

Table 2. Utilization of production capacity in textile industries dynamics, %.

Textile networks	2020 y.	2021 y.	2022 y.	2023 y.
1. Cotton fiber	50,7	76,1	77,3	80,0
2. Thread production	66,1	73,1	75,8	81,0
3. Production of raw syrup	64,5	75,6	78,0	80,0
4. Production of finished yarn gauze	64,2	77,5	80,1	83,0
5. Production of non-woven materials	63,7	74,3	77,8	80,0
6. Production of knitted fabric	64,6	73,5	78,0	89,0
7. Production of knitted goods	63,4	69,1	80,4	90,0

The analysis of knitting enterprises within the network indicates that in 2020, the production volume of knitted fabric was 49,400 tons, which increased to 53,400 tons in 2021, reflecting a growth rate of 108%. For 2022, the planned production volume of knitted fabric was 69,900 tons, with an anticipated growth rate of 131%. Currently, 78% of production capacity is utilized in knitting enterprises, indicating that there are internal opportunities for increased production through the full utilization of existing capacities.

The company is also focused on producing import-substituting products and thoroughly analyzing the import structure of its subsidiaries. In 2022, imports amounted to 165.6 million US dollars, with 99.4 million attributed to equipment and spare parts, comprising 60% of total imports.

The global economic crisis has impacted production in many countries, prompting the company to implement measures to mitigate the negative effects of the financial downturn, ensure stable economic growth, and maintain macroeconomic balance. These initiatives aim to support employment, assist exporters, and promote small businesses. In 2022 alone, 12,536 new jobs were created, including 1,265 through household enterprises. Efforts to reduce product costs – targeting a decrease of 6.3% – are being implemented through the efficient use of raw materials and energy resources, optimization of production facilities, increased labor productivity, and the reduction of non-production costs. As a result, in 2022, the cost of products at the company's enterprises decreased by 17.1 billion soums.

Currently, the "Uztoqimaliksanoat" association is undertaking various initiatives to enhance labor productivity, fill the domestic market with quality products, increase export potential, and create additional jobs. Additionally, producing competitive products for the global market through diversification and the introduction of new technologies remains a pressing priority.

Textiles and light industry are among the most labor-intensive sectors. By increasing production volumes in network enterprises and establishing new facilities, many new jobs can be created – providing employment opportunities and improving living standards. In 2023, it is planned to create over 12,500 new jobs in network enterprises through modernization and the establishment of new production units. This will help meet the demand for high-quality textile and light industrial products, provide new employment opportunities, and enhance the population's standard of living.

The implementation of state investment programs is of particular importance in the development of the textile industry. In 2017, investments amounted to 179.4 million US dollars. In 2018, 101.5 million US dollars of foreign direct investments were attracted. In 2019, this figure increased to 117 million US dollars.

The textile industry, as one of the most promising sectors of the republic's economy, includes several segments that produce finished products. In addition, it employs a large part of the workforce, thereby serving as a key source of employment. However, the current structure of the textile industry does not fully meet existing demand: production efficiency and product quality remain low, and economic and social imbalances within the sector call for a comprehensive approach to modernization and innovation. Enterprises in this sector are notable not only for their high labor intensity, but also for their flexibility in locating production, establishing branches, and launching small enterprises across nearly all regions of the republic.

Among the factors slowing down the development of textile industry enterprises, we can include such elements as low labor productivity, ineffective use of existing techniques and technologies, shortage of qualified workers and specialists, and a low level of qualification among existing personnel. In addition to these, the fact that the prices of raw materials and components supplied to enterprises are increasing faster than the prices of finished products negatively impacts the development of the industry.

Therefore, the development of all branches of the textile industry that produce finished products – and, as a result, the inclusion of these products in the export structure on a permanent basis, not limited to the domestic scale – and ensuring export growth have a significant impact not only on the sector's development but also on the national income of the republic. Currently, this sector – that is, the textile industry – accounts for more than 20% of Uzbekistan's gross national income. One-third of the employed population works in this sector, and in different years, the textile industry has made

up 25% to 28% of the state budget's income. It is evident that the development of the textile industry and its branches, the increase in export potential and competitiveness, as well as the specialization in import-substituting product manufacturing, have a direct influence on the growth of the national income.

From the above, it can be concluded that the textile industry currently occupies a strategically important position in the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Interest in this sector is steadily growing. The industry supplies 20% of domestic consumer goods and has high employment and export potential. Therefore, it should continue to hold a significant place in enhancing the economic and production potential of the country.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

As the textile sector focuses on producing consumer goods, it plays a vital role in industrial production, significantly saturating domestic markets. As of 2023-01-01, the "Uztoqimaliksanoat" association comprises 1,512 industrial enterprises, including 369 textile companies and 1,143 operating in the knitwear and knitting sector.

According to Presidential Resolution No. 2687 issued on 2018-12-21, the goal for 2023 is to increase cotton fiber processing to 76%. Strategies have been outlined to ensure that 100% of cotton raw materials produced in the republic are fully processed, aiming to boost product exports by 2.5 times and to triple production volumes.

Currently, the production capacities of weaving enterprises within the "Uztoqimaliksanoat" association are not being fully utilized, presenting internal opportunities for expanding output through optimization of existing facilities.

Considering emerging market conditions, production volumes at enterprises under the "Uztoqimaliksanoat" umbrella are growing by an average of 18–20% annually. This growth contributes to a significant influx of domestically produced textile, knitwear, and sewn products into the local market.

At present, the "Uztoqimaliksanoat" association is actively working to enhance labor productivity, saturate the domestic market with high-quality products, increase export potential, and create new jobs. Furthermore, the production of competitive goods for the global market through diversification and the introduction of new technologies remains a top priority.

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2025. № 4

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"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
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Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

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